

Literary Analysis of Selected Nigeria-Biafra War Songs (1967 - 1970)

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Abstract:

War songs played a pivotal role during the Nigerian-Biafra war fought from 1967 to 1970. The songs provide warrior's thoughts, feelings, and mood to fight for the liberation of the Igbo people. Thus, study is focused in literary analysis of selected Nigerian-Biafra war songs, identify the theme embedded in the war songs and examine the literary devices used in the selected war songs. Fifteen Nigerian-Biafra war songs were selected for the study. Both primary and secondary data were sourced for the analysis. The primary data collection was obtained through recording, face-to-face interview and observations. The secondary data were sourced from documents which have some war songs in print. The study is premised on speech accommodation theory. The findings of the study revealed that there are various themes embedded in Nigerian-Biafra war songs that make reference to the history and culture of the Igbo people and the tensions and harmonies – within the Nigeria society from which these songs were drawn. Furthermore, the study revealed that most Nigerian-Biafra war songs are structurally composed in single stanzas. The study also revealed that the Nigerian-Biafra war songs are rendered in simple and compound sentences and full of repetitions, metaphorical expressions, parallelisms, symbolisms that help to communicate clear messages and intents of warriors.

keywords: Song, War Songs, Style, Structure and Theme.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Igbo war songs (abụ agha) during the Nigerian-Biafra war (1967-1970) were essential tools for the propaganda, boosting morale, and fostering a sense of, and national identity among the Igbo people and other Biafrans. These songs often utilized traditional imagery-referencing lions, leopards, and rams – to depict leaders and soldiers as courageous and to dehumanize the enemy. The songs, slogans that are performed during the war instill hope in the warriors and encourage them to continue the fight until they attain victory.

In Nigeria and among the Igbo people in particular, the song is one of the main connections between man and his creator and serves as his constant companion. There are songs to accompany the thing one does from birth to death, songs to guide the spirit of the dead to the world – beyond this one. There are songs also that go with every facet of our life such as child birth, death, works, hunting, war, marriage, chieftaincy coronation to mention but just a few. Samortey (2012) opines that songs are very important forms of communication. Through songs, one can identify some important people and the legacies they have left behind in society as well as why and how certain things are done among some groups of people.

Songs, as an element of oral literature, preserve the language of a people. It contains their beliefs and traditions and war songs are not exception. Most of the activities of the Igbo people demand some accomplishment of songs to investigate them for effective productivity. Matiza and Mutasa (2020) posit that war songs provoke people's thoughts, feelings, and moods to fight for the liberation of one's country and also instill hope in bora the liberation fighters and the masses as the songs give the warriors strength to continue fighting until victory is attained. In spite of the importance of war songs, much is not known about Nigerian-Biafra war songs. Moreover, some people even perceived war songs for idol worshippers, hence the youth of today shun them. These songs are structured and styled – with literary devices which appeal to the emotions of the fighters to fight harder.

Igbo war songs are one of the most important weapons of war among the Igbo people. War songs are normally sung by warriors before, during and after war to express sentiments under the leadership of a war Lord. It can also be sung individually by a war Lord to either dare the enemy to fight them, to expose the weakness of their enemy or to inspire the warriors to pit their bravery to test.

1.1 Igbo people and their language

The Igbo people are a major ethnic group in Nigeria, numbering over 30-40 million, primarily inhabiting the southeastern region known as Igbo land. The Igbo are renowned for their republican, democratic social structure, entrepreneurial spirit, and rich cultural heritage. They speak the Igbo language, a tonal language from the Niger-Congo family.

The Igbo people are primarily located in southeastern Nigeria (Anambra, Abia, Imo, Ebonyi and Enugu) they are also found in Delta and Rivers States with significant diaspora populations in Cameroon and Equatorial Guinea. The Igbo people are

historically organized into decentralized, autonomous village groups. The Igbo people emphasize kinship, and they are known for their art, music, and the cultivation of yams as a staple crop. Igbo has over thirty (30) distinct dialects. A standardized form (Igbo Izugbe) was developed for literary and educational purposes in the 1970s. The Igbo people are known for their resilience, particularly during the 1967-1970 Nigerian Civil War.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature related to this study is reviewed under the following sub-headings: conceptual framework, empirical studies and theoretical framework.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Under conceptual framework, the following concepts were explained in relation to the present study. They are; Song, War Songs, style and the theme.

2.1.1 Song

Palmer (1965) defines song as the art of combining sounds or tones for reproduction by voice or by various kinds of musical instruments in rhythmic, melodic and harmonic form so as to effect emotion. Judson (1979) also defines song as sounds made by voices or instruments arranged in a way that is pleasant to listen to. According to Banks (1996), a song is an art of sound that expresses ideas and emotions in significant forms through the elements of rhythms, melody, harmony and colour. In the context of this study, song is a composition in verse form that verbally expresses ideas, thoughts and emotion. A song is a short poem or other set of words set to music or meant to be sung. In African societies almost all communal activities are accompanied by song and dance. In most societies there are songs for every stage and occasion of person's life, from the cradle to the grave. There are songs at birth, naming ceremonies, war, imitation, praise songs, work songs, divination songs, funeral songs among others.

2.1.2 War songs

Aborchie (2011) opines that a war song is a song warriors sing when they are ready for war or after a war. It is a piece of music closely connected to war or battle, either sung while at war front or battle to coordinate timing or linked to a task. These war songs have literary devices such as repetition, symbolism, metaphor, run-on-line among others. These songs give the fighters the morale to continue fighting and give them confidence that they would win the struggle. Matiza and Mutasa (2020) add that, the slogans, songs and music that are performed during the war instill hope in the warriors and encourage them to continue the fight until they attain victory. Azuonye (1979) opines that war songs are a universal literary phenomenon that occurs in the oral traditions of all formerly warlike societies as reminders of the poetic spirit with which heroic ancestors confronted danger on the battlefield in pursuit of honour. Such songs are not only chanted by warriors on their way home from successful expeditions, they are also chanted in the

course of actual combat on the battlefield to sustain the momentum of the attack and to demoralize the enemy. According to Azuonye, war songs can be categorized into three main distinctions; (i) preparatory battle songs (ii) operational battle songs, and (iii) celebrating battle songs. This study will adopt the definition put forward by Aborchie (2011) as its working definition.

2.1.3 Style

Martindale (1991) defines style as the habitual way in which a given individual or group chooses to communicate their ideas, whether through language, art, music or other forms of expression. Martindale's definition of style emphasizes the uniqueness in communication based on context and intentions. Also, Fowler (2025) opines that style is the effective and appropriate use of language features such as syntax, diction, and tone to achieve a desired rhetorical effect. In the same light, Barthes (1997) new style as the way in which language is used to convey meaning, including both explicit and implicit messages through various linguistic devices and techniques. Eco (1986) defines style as the result of the interaction between an author's individual expression and the cultural historical and social context in which it is situated, shaping the form and content of a text. In the context of this study, style refers to the way a writer uses words and expressions to present ideas in a literary work. It includes the writer's choice of vocabulary, sentence structure, tone, and use of literary devices. Language style makes a writer's work unique and helps to communicate meaning effectively.

2.1.4 Theme

A theme from lay man's point of view is the central idea in any literary work or oral piece. Every oral art has a specific message that it intends to convey or carry to its audience. It is worth noting that, themes, to some extent a related from one ethnic group to the other.

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on discourse Analysis Framework Propounded by Fairclough (1989). Discourse analysis approach examines functions of the sings, the incorporated cultures, and the semantic attributes of expressions used. Discourse analysis is a broad, interdisciplinary approach to analyzing written, spoken, or sign language within its social, cultural, and historical context. It moves beyond examining isolated words or sentences to understand how language is used in real-life situations to convey meaning and perform actions. The fundamental idea behind discourse analysis is that language is not neutral, instead, it actively shapes our understanding of the world, construct solid reality, and influence social structures. Discourse analysis examines how the surrounding circumstances – social, cultural, historical, and the relationship between participants – affect the meaning of the language used. The analysis focus on how meaning is made and why certain linguistic choices are made in a specific context, rather than just literal definitions of words. Language is understood as a form of social action.

2.3 PREVIOUS STUDIES

Ugochukwu (2012) worked on songs on the battlefield- Biafra's powerful weapon. The study examined the role of war songs. The study was based on a 1969 recording of sixteen songs in Igbo, English and Ijo. These songs were recorded in aid of the Biafran Red Cross at the height of the civil war, 16km away from the frontline, just before the fall of Biafra's make-shift capital, Umuahia. The study compares those songs with other, noted down by journalists visiting the enclave in 1968-69 and with those inserted in Igbo novels and memoirs published after the war. Offering a thematic study of the texts, their, their oral root, their style, structure and language, it reveals their power to impact the morale of civilians and soldiers alike, and shed some light on the reasons behind their inclusion in writings from Adichie, Agu, Akuneme, Aniebo, Ekwensi and Nwachukwu-Agbada. Anyanwu (2023) carried out a study on the survivalist relief songs of appreciation and condemnation.

The Nigerian-Biafra civil war of 1967-1970 unleashed several creative survival strategies among the Igbo. One of such strategies manifested in the composition of songs designed to address perceived inequalities and injustice experienced during the period. This study adopted the key informant interview, participant observation and historical-analytic approaches to interrogate some of the songs composed during the period by civilians with reference to the sharing of relief materials, mostly foodstuff, in appreciation of their benefactors and condemnation of their oppressors. The objective of the study was to document for posterity some of these songs which have been glossed over by war historians and scholars and show how the Igbo were able to handle some of the negative effects of the war using music and songs. Five songs, drawn from the oral repertoire, hitherto undocumented in any form, were discussed, four of which were related to relief materials and one on the war itself. It was found that songs have the capacity to rejuvenate, motivate, reinforce and enliven the spirit. The study concluded that songs of various kinds help human beings cope and endure difficult situations such as war.

Anyachonkeya (2015) worked on discourse analysis of language of war songs. The objective of the study was to conduct a discourse analysis of language of war songs. The study seeks to ascertain the extent to which war songs could serve as tonic or psychological therapy to the entire people (civil and combatant forces) in war situation. The study singled out war songs used during the Biafran war of survival, the document of which makes the historical document and serves as memento to the present generation of Nigerian youths especially the youths of the defunct Eastern Region whose region made up the short-lived breakaway Republic of Biafra. Those songs buoyed up the morale of the Biafran civil population as well as the combatant armed forces.

Atata and Omobowale (2015) worked on the social symbolism of Biafra protest songs in southeastern Nigeria. The objective of the study was to explain the symbolism of Biafra protest songs in southeastern Nigeria. Protest is essential element of democratization process and a significant factor in the social struggle and commitment to a cause. Protests are staged in different forms, either, with placards or songs to portray

socio-political grievance. Protest songs are symbols that contextualize intent of a social struggle. The protest songs depict cultural and group ideology, which fosters the Igbo identity cohesion in the Biafra struggle. These protest songs indicate shared patterns of behaviour and interaction, cognitive constructs and understanding that create unique symbolism of Biafra among the Igbo people of Nigeria. The study established that Biafra protest songs are a non-material culture that contextualizes the meaning attached to Biafra in achieving identity- capital, identity cohesion, struggle sustenance and commitment during protest.

Okuyade (2010) researched on the re-articulation of hope from cries: Nigeria civil war poetry as ledger. The study attempted to re-examine the poetry of Nigerian civil war to bring to the foreground the disasters it brought upon Nigerians and to caution the generation who did not experience the war, especially the youths on the dangers of resolving socio-political crisis through violence even without one. Invariably, the study examines poetry written by soldiers who were directly involved in the war, civilians who experienced the war closely or remotely and poets who wrote two decades after the war. From a contrapuntal reading, the poetry of the Nigerian civil war becomes a documentation of hope for a wounded society because of the substantive way it dealt with the traditional themes of the integrity of the individual or the nation's collective destiny during and after the war. The study established that since the testimony of the Nigerian civil war has translated into an historical reality, the war story will continue to be of strategic importance for Nigerians.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research

The study employs a description research design of representing data because the data does not involve numbers but rather a description of characters or performance.

3.2 Method of data collection

Data for the study were collected through primary and secondary sources. The primary sources of data collection include interview, observation, audio-recording and note taking. The secondary sources of data collection include journal articles, thesis and document observation.

3.3 Method of data analysis

The raw data collected from the respondents were transcribed. Fifteen war songs were analyzed under the structure, style and themes and their literary devices were also examined. The war songs were transcribed into the English language. The collected data were then analyzed descriptively.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This section discusses and analyses the data collected on selected Nigerian-Biafra war songs in terms of structure, theme and literary devices used in the songs. The terms lead singer, and chorus are represented by L.S and CH. Respectively in analyzing the songs.

a. Song text 1: Anyị bụ ụmụ agha- We are children of war

L.S: Anyị bụ ụmụ agha	-	We are children of war
Anyị bụ ụmụ agha	-	We are children of war
CH: Mma anaghị egbu anyị	-	We are not killed by matchets
Me mgbọ anaghị egbu anyị	-	And we are not killed by bullet
Mmeri bụ nke anyị oge nile	-	Victory is always ours

The war song text 1 above is a preparatory war song. Azuonye (1979) posits that preparatory war song is a variety of battle songs with which warriors traditionally marched to battle. Singing these songs, their performers brandish their guns and matchets with gestures imitating the courage with which the warriors of old made their often-risky journey through thick forest in which potential head hunters generally lurked.

Structure

Song text 1 is structure in one stanza with five lines. It has a cell and response structure. The first two lines are made up of five words each. The third line is made up of four lines, the fourth line is made up of five lines and the fifth line is made up of six lines.

Theme

The theme of this song is confidence. The warriors are trumpeting that they are not killed by machetes or bullet. Therefore, they have confidence in them that their enemies would be defeated and they would come with a victory. This can be found in the last line “Mmeri bụ nke anyị oge niile,” which means victory is always ours.

Literary devices or style

The language used in this song is simple and plain. It is short and brief that any ordinary person can understand. The songs contain literary device such as repetition. The lead singer repeats the first line in line two before the chorus also repeats what the lead singer sings. The repetitive nature of the song makes it beautiful for the warrior to enjoy. The matchets and bullet symbolizes their enemies on the battlefield (Fairclough, 1989).

b. Song text 2: Onye Akpakwala Nwa Agụ Aka n' Ọdụ- Let no one touch the lion by the tail

L.S: Gowon ị metekwe nwa agụ dī n; ụra-	Gowon if you dare wake the sleeping lion
CH: Mgbe nwa agụ tetere ebelebe egbuo-be	When the cub awakens, how tagic it will
L.S: kweke kweke	- Kweke kweke
CH: Ebule ji isi e je ọgụ	- The Ram goes to battle with his head
L.S: Onye akpakwala nwa agụ aka n' ọdụ-	Let mo one touch the lion by the tail
CH: Ma ọ di ndụ	- Whether it is alive
CH: Ma ọ nwụrụ anwụ	- Whether it is dead
L.S: Onye akpakwala nwa agụ aka n' ọdụ	-Let no one touch the lion by the tail

The war song in text 2 is a preparatory war song. In the song, the singer is first warning Gowon the then head of state not to touch the tail of the sleeping lion for wakening the sleeping lion will be disastrous.

Structure

The song is in one stanza with eight lines. The first line contains seven words, second line 6 words; third line, two words, fourth line, six words; fifth line is six words, sixth and seventh lines, four words each and the eight contains six words.

Theme

The theme of this song is valour which means fearlessness or boldness. The warriors are trumpeting that they should their enemies if they dare attack them.

Literary devices

This war song is in single and plain language. The song uses onomatopoeia – “kweke kweke”. Here “kweke kweke” is used to denote how ram uses its horn to fight. Enjambment is another type literary device used in the war song. The word enjambment is a French word meaning “a striding over” & a poetic term for continuation of sentence or phrase from one line of poetry to the next. It is also known as run online. This is another artistic device used in the Nigeria-Biafra war song above as follows:

Kweke kweke
Ebulie ji isi eje ọgụ

The dominant device used in the song is repetition. The chorus repeats the first two lines of the lead singer. Line five is repeated in line eighth.

Symbolism. In the study ‘Agụ’ is a symbol of strenght. The singer is trumpeting that they will crush their thee way lion crushes anyonee that dares his way.

c. Song text 3: Ikemba ndi Igbo-

General Ojukwu
 Ikemba ndi Igbo
 Eze ndi Igbo gburugburu
 Nwa huru ala nna ya n' anya
 Mgbe Igbo juru onye ka ha ga-eziga
 i kwuputa si ha ziga gi
 Ojukwu
 I ji ogbunigwe gwoo
 Ndi iro gi iba na Mkpoo
 Jiri shoo batiri suo ha
 Akwu n' oshimiri Naija
 Ojukwu
 Nkenke enyi churu igwe
 Enyi oso
 Nwa egbe nkanka nku
 Onye gwere ndi iro
 Ka ose n' Uzakoli
 O bu Ojukwu
 Ikemba
 Anyi ji gi eme onu n' ututu
 Anyi ji gi eme onu n' abali
 Nnoo
 Eze ndi Igbo

The pillar of Igbo nation

- General Ojukwu
 - The pillar of Igbo nation
 - King of all the Igbo nations
 - Lover of his father land
 - When the Igbo asked for who to send
 - You volunteered yourself for the big task
 - Ojukwu
 - You used Ogbunigwe to massacre
 - The enemies at Mkpoo
 - You grind them with shore
 - Battery at river Niger
 - Ojukwu
 - The little elephant that
 - Defeated a multitude of elephant
 - A hard slein warrior
 - Who killed thousands of enemies
 - At Uzakoli
 - It is Ojukwu
 - The Pillar of the nation
 - We are proud of you in the morning
 - We are proud of you in the evening
 - Welcome
 - King of the Igbo nation

Structure

The war song is structured in one stanza with twenty lines with a mixture of short and long lines.

Theme

The theme of this war song is praise of a mighty warrior. The songster is proclaiming that when they searched warriors for war, they could find one, Ojukwu, who volunteered to go.

As the songster puts it:

Mgbe Igbo juru onye ka ha ga-eziga - When the Igbo asked for who to send
 i kwuputara si ha ziga gi - You volunteered yourself for the big task

To show that Ojukwu was a warrior, the songster puts it.

I ji ogbunigwe gwoo ndi - You used ogbunigwe to
 Iro gi iba na Mkpoo - Massacre the enemies at Mkpoo

Jiri shọọ batiri sọ ha - You grind them with shore
Akwu n' oshimiri Naija - Battery at river Niger

The war song above is a preparatory war song. Warriors or fighter sing this song as a warm up exercise to get themselves prepared. This song inspires the Warriors and gives them more hope for victory. The songster is announcing that they searching for a man they can send to the war front. It could also mean that when the opponents think they are powerful, they also have somebody on their side who is mightier than them.

Structure

The war song above is structured in one stanza.

Theme

The theme of this war song is mighty warrior. The songster is proclaiming that when they searched for Warriors, they could find one, Ojukwu, the war lord who volunteered to go and wage war against Nigerian State.

Literary devices or style

The war song text is written in simple and plain language. The song contains some literary devices such as metaphor as seen in line 8, “ I jiri ogbonigwe gwọọ ndi iro gi iba na Mkpọọ” (You used ogbunigwe to massacre the enemies at enemies at Mkpọọ) and “jiri shọọ batiri sọ ha akwu n' oshimiri Niaja” (you grind them with shore battery at river Niger). It is short and self-explanatory and that everybody can hear and understand. It contains some literary devices such as repetition and enjambment.

Repetition is also used as literary device in the war song as sen in song text 3 lines 16,17 and 18;

Anyi ji gi eme onu - we are proud of you
Anyi ji gi eme onu - we are proud of you
Anyi ji gi eme onu - we are proud of you

The repetitive nature of the song makes it interesting and enjoyable and also makes it very easy for other warriors and masses to join in the singing. This song aim at reassuring the audience about the qualities of their leaders by enumerating their heroic tradition, which gives them a rich love of texts, images and themes, guarantees credibility and builds them into a modern nationalist movement. The Biafran hero is the head of state, showered with traditional little-inspired by Igbo cultural symbolism as the except below illustrates:

d. Song text 4: Ojukwu bu Eze Biafra- Ojukwu is the king of Biafra

Ojukwu bu Eze Biafra	-	Ojukwu is the king of biafra
Echiri ya	-	he was crowned
Na Aburi	-	at Aburi
Awolowo, Yakubu Gowon	-	Awolowo, Yakubu Gowon
Ha enweghi ike imeri Biafra	-	they cannot defeat Biafra

e. Song text 5: Nzogbu Nzogbu- Stamping stamping

Nzogbu Nzogbu	-	stamp down your feet and kill whoever is there
Enyi mba enyi	-	we are mighty nation, we are
Nzogbu	-	Stamp down your feet and kill
Enyi mba enyi	-	We are the mighty nation, we are
Nzogbu nwoke	-	stamp down and kill any man across your way
Enyi mba enyi	-	we are mighty nation, we are
Nzogbu nwaanyi	-	Stamp down and kill any woman across your way
Enyi mba enyi	-	We are the mighty nation, we are
Nzogbu	-	Stamp down your feet and kill
Enyi mba enyi	-	we are mighty nation, we are
Nzogbu	-	stamp down your feet and kill

Nzogbu nzogbu is a is a traditional Igbo song usually rendered while fighting against an enemy. The song describes community's strength like the strength of an elephant that crushes all obstacles on its way. It symbolically constructs community's bonding and unity against a common enemy as the elephant's strength through which victory is assured. The war songs motivate and propel armless Biafra warriors against fully armed security forces of the state, under the assumption of victory someday. The war song shows bravery and willingness to fight for Biafra amidst violence.

Repetition is a key literary device in this war song. Thus, 'Nzogbu' and 'Enyi mba enyi' were repeated several times to emphasize the point and create artistic beauty (rhythm). As the conflict wore on, the enthusiasm which marked the early days, the admiration showered on the leaders and the people's faith in their troop' ability to achieve success were all deeply affected by repeated defeats and human losses, and too often, despondency and despair set in. Songs poignantly expressed those feelings as the enemy armaments, its armored car, shelling machine, heavy artillery. New patriotic songs were them created to try and counter act those feelings. They first reminded their audience of the recent past and pogroms that had justified the succession in the first place as the song below illustrates:

f. Song text 6: Iwe iwe iwe- Anger Anger Anger

Iwe, iwe, iwe----- Anger, anger, anger
Iwe--- Anger
Iwe na-ewe anyi- We are angry
Iwe Angry
Iwe na-ewe anyi- We are angry

Na ha gburu nwanne anyi- Because they killed our brother
This is one stanza poem with six lines.

Theme: The theme of this poem is anger. The warriors are expressing their anger over the massacre of their brothers in the Northern Nigeria in 1966.

Song texts 5 and 6 have theme of commitment and anger. Commitment expressed a dedication to a cause against all odds. The Biafra war songs, whether spontaneously created or adapted from an existing collection exalt Igbo commitment to the Biafra cause. The song encourages every supporter of Biafra to join the war and be committed to it till death as the excerpt below illustrates:

Biafra, Biafra
Biafra, Biafra- Biafra, Biafra
Biafra ka m ga-eso- I will follow Biafra
Ma m ga-anwu-- Even if I shall die
Ma m ga-adi ndu-- Even if I shall live
Biafra ka m ga-eso- I shall follow Biafra

The song projects Biafra nationalism. The warriors chant that they are committed to Biafra unto death. It is like a call chant of patriotism. In the hearts and minds of the Biafra warriors, Biafra is a state, unto whose sovereignty they have sworn and committed their lives to see to fruition.

g. Song text 8: Umunna m, Hausa mere anyi ofu o- Hausa people massacred our people

Umunna m - My family member
Hausa mere anyi ofu o - Hausa people massacred our people
Ha gburu anyi o - They killed our people
Hausa mere anyi ekwuekwu - they treated us badly
Amuna amu - They made us see our ears with our eye
Umunna, ewo! - My brother, ewo !
Ha gbusili anyi n' ugwu Hausa - They killed our people in the north
Me anyi ka anyi aburo mmadu ma ncha - Treated us as if we are not human
Si anyi ekwuna - And told us to be silent

Koa anyi gabanu ugwu Hausa	-	Let us go to the Northern State
Ogu Hausa aburo ogu mmadu	-	fight against Hausa people is not
Na-agbalu oso	-	What people should fear and run
away		

Many of the Biafra war songs express deep love for the homeland, a theme summarized by two of the songs and which stroke a cord with the refugees and the displaced that crowded the roles and villages.

h. Song text 9:

Anyi egbuola ha	Anyi egbuola ha
Anyi egbuola ha--	We have killed them
Anyi egbuola ha--	We have killed them
Anyi egbuola ha n'ehihie-	We have killed them in the afternoon
Eihie a adiro ha mma--	This afternoon did not favour them
Njinji jiri n'Abagana--	Catastrophe befall in Abagana
Chi were ehie jie n'Abagana--	Night befall afternoon in Abagana
Umū agu egbuola ha-	The wolves have killed them
Anyi egbuola ha n'ehihie--	We have killed them in the afternoon
Eihie ubochi ahū adiroha mma--	The afternoon of that day did not favour them.

The war song above is a celebrative war song. The Biafra warriors were jubilating and trumpeting that they killed their enemies during the battle at Abagana in Anambra state. The song is a call and response. The lead singer did mention wolves which are the brain behind the killing. Wolves are wild animals and fearful animals that can kill a human being. In this case they are using wolves to refer to the Biafran warlords like Odumegwu Ojukwu and Chukwuma Nzeogwu.

Structure

The song above is structured in one block stanza of nine lines. The first and second lines have three words each. Line three has four words while line four has five words. Line five has four words, line six has five words. Line seven has four words while line eight also has four words and line nine has six words.

Theme

The theme of the war song is victory is won. The warriors were shouting and trumpeting that they have killed their enemies in large number. They killed them throughout the afternoon that day so the afternoon did not favour their enemies which means that they were victorious.

i. Song text 10: Ebe ka Ụnu Si?-

L.S: Ebe ke unu si?	-	Where do you come from?
CH: Biafra	-	Biafra
L.S: Ebe ka unu si?	-	Where do you come from?
CH: Biafra	-	Biafra
L.S: Agaghị m ahapụ Biafra	-	I will not leave Biafra
CH: Je n' ebe ọzọ ga-biri	-	And go to live elsewhere
L.S: Biafra ga-adị ndu	-	Biafra will survive

Singing was a way of fighting ones fear and the temptation to abscond and run away, at a time when some grabbed every opportunity to leave the embattled country. It helped forget the omnipresence of death and the uncertain future.

j. Song text 11: Biafra, Biafra

Biafra, Biafra	-	Biafra Biafra
Biafra ka m ga-eso	-	Biafra i shall follow
Ma m ga-anwụ anwụ	-	whether I am dying
Ma m ga-adị ndu	-	or I am Living

Naba na Ndokwa

Naba na ndokwa		
Ugwu, naba na ndokwa	-	Ugwu, go in peace
Ọ ga-adili gi mma	-	It will be well with you
Naba na ndokwa	-	Go in peace

This is dirge the soldiers sang on the wake keeping in honour of the young Ugwu, presumed dead in battle, after they searched in vain for this body. The dirge below is the dirge the soldiers sang on the road in honour of major Chukwuma Kaduna Nzeogwu, fallen on the Nsukka front in the first hours of the war in 1967.

k. Song text 12: Commando Nzeogwu - Commander Nzeogwu

Commando Nzeogwu	-	Commander Nzeogwu
Anyị anaa	-	Let us retreat
Nekwanụ Nzeogwu oo	-	Look at Nzeogwu oo
Gị na-abara anyị mba	-	You that is taunting us
Nzeogwu nọ na front anwụrugo	-	Nzeogwu in the battle field is dead
Nzeogwu nwanne m oo	-	Nzeogwu my brother oo
Ubochị Gowon ga-eme uche ya	-	the day Gowon will retaliate
Na Nzeogwu amarasigo	-	Nzeogwu is already aware

Praise song

L. Song text 13: Chukwu Gozie Gabon (God bless Gabon)

Gabon eee, Chukwu gozie unu o	-	Gabon eh, God bless you
Gabon eee, a si m ka m kelee unu o	-	Gabon, I say thank you
Unu nyere anyi oka ka umu rie di ndu	-	You gave us corn so the children of men Eat and live
Unu nyere anyi nri ka Biafra	-	You offered us food so the
Rie di ndu o	-	Children of Biafra should eat and stay alive
Oh ho ho oh oh sambo sambola	-	oh ho ho ho ho sambo sambola
Oh ho ho oh oh sambo sambola	-	oh ho ho ho ho sambo sambola.

The song above reflect the Igbo collective sense and shared understanding of hard work, generosity and appreciation. In the war, torn villages of Igbo land, when food was scarce and the risk of getting any farm produce at its maximum, it was grateful hearts that the Largesse from Gabon was welcomed by both the civilian population and military. The song was therefore a means of showing their appreciation for the gestures, hence the lyrics, Gabon, may God bless you.'

m. Song text 14: I Meela, Ojukwu - Thank You, Ojukwu

I meela, Ojukwu, I meela	-	Thank you Ojukwu, thank you
I meela, Ojukwu, I meela	-	Thank you Ojukwu, thank you
A ga m esore umaka we gaa soja	-	I will join the army with my peers
Were akwukwo rekereke turu n' isi	-	-Using rekereke leaves to decorate my head.
Ka m gbagbuonu Gowon onye Awusa	-	To shoot to death Gowon the Hausa
I meela, Ojukwu, I meela	-	Thank you Ojukwu, thank you

This song was used to praise Ojukwu and thank him for giving the snipers the opportunity to go to war in order to kill Gowon, the Hausa man. It is worthy to note that it was worse for the Biafran youths as they had only locally fabricated guns if at all and lacked the most basic military training. Yes, they were proud that they were going into battle with the mandate to kill Gowon, the Hausa man.

n. Song text 15: Ma ogbo anyi ejeghi agha- If our age mate do not go to war

Ma ogbo anyi ejeghi agha-If our age mate do not go to war?
Onye ga-eje agha- Who will then go to war?
Agha oo agha oo agha- War oo war oo war
Ma ogbo anyi ejeghi agha- If our age mate do not go to war?
Onye ga-eje agha- Who will then go to war?

Agha oo agha oo agha- War oo war oo war
Okooko okooko e- Okooko okooko e
Okooko okooko e- Okooko okooko e
Agha oḡbọ anyị- War for our age mate

Theme

The theme of this song is that of awakening. The Biafran warriors were calling the youth to join in the war against Nigerian State.

Structure

The song has only one stanza with nine lines. Repetition is the key literary device in the song. The song is rhythmic in nature.

o. Song text 16: Onye ga-ebu agha?- Who will wage the war?

Onye ga-ebu agha?-- Who will wage the war?
Ụmụ Biafra ga-ebu agha- Biafran children will wage the war
Onye ga-ebu agha?-- Who will wage the war?
Ụmụ Biafra ga-ebu agha- Biafran children will wage the war
Agha agha agha- War war war
Anyị ga-ebu agha- We shall wage the war
Megide Gowon, agha- War against Gowon, war
Megide Naijiria- War against Nigeria
Megide Ugwu Awusa- War against Hausa people in the north
Onye ga-ebu agha?- Who will wage the war?

Theme

The theme of this song is self-determination

Structure

The war song has one stanza with ten lines. The song contains simple sentences that one can easily comprehend.

Literary device or style

The literary device used in the song is mostly rhetorical questions.

5. FINDINGS

The study established that war songs have the capacity to rejuvenate, motivate, reinforce and enliven the spirit of the warriors. It was also found that songs of various kinds help human beings cope and endure situations, which would be difficult to handle without such songs.

The study further revealed that Nigeria-Biafra war songs instill hope in the warriors and encourage them to continue the fight until they attain victory. War songs

provoke people's thoughts, feelings, and mood to fight for the liberation of their people. War songs help in boosting the warriors; morale

The study also revealed that the songs are structurally composed in a single stanza. There were some enjambments in most of the song texts. They structured in simple sentences and full of repetitions. The war songs are mostly call-and-response types of songs.

Furthermore, the study established that Nigerian-Biafra war songs have different themes such as victory, valour, bravery, confidence, encouragement among others. These Nigerian-Biafra war songs can be categorized into three main stages: preparatory, operational and celebrative.

6. CONCLUSION

The study analysed the structure, style and themes in Nigerian-Biafra war songs. It was established that the songs have structure and contain various themes. The Nigerian-Biafra war songs contain various literary devices such as repetition, metaphor, symbolism, rhetorical questions and enjambment among others.

These literary devices play great significant roles in the songs and the warriors. It further observed that repetition is the most common literary devices which can be found in the songs. The study further established that repetition in the songs was to make interesting, enjoyable and easy to learn and memorize. The themes and structure of the war songs were established. Such established themes include: bravery, confidence, valour, victory and encouragement. The war songs were mostly structured in one stanza with call-and-response mode of delivery.

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